

www.arseam.com

Impact Factor: 1.13

PROTECTION OF NATURE'S SCENIC BEAUTY HAS AN IMPORTANT ROLE IN THE GROWTH OF ECOTOURISM : (A CASE STUDY OF WAYANAD DISTRICT)

Anita Jose

Ph. D. Scholar ,Bharathiar University,
Cochin

Dr Sibu. C . Chithran

Ph.D supervisor,
Bharathiar University, Cochin

ABSTRACT

Tourism is an industry which occurs at destination areas, with different natural or manmade attraction to attract non local people. Eco tourism means responsible travel to natural areas that conserves the environment and improves the well being of local people. Tourism facilities should be particularly designed in an environment friendly way, since they are located in areas of great scenic beauty and ecological significance. It is always important to have tourism facilities which are in harmony with the surrounding environment (both natural and cultural). This can be achieved by using architectural forms with the natural landscape (vegetation and land forms). A tourism facility should always possess a sense of place. Wayanad is blessed by Mother Nature: its vast stretches of mist capped mountains, green meadows of valleys, white water springs, blue water lakes and wild forests fabricate the splendid natural beauty. A geographical study is based on field work in Wayanad. The Primary data collected by visiting Wayanad and Secondary was data collected from published materials.

Key Words: - Eco-tourism, Environment friendly, Architectural forms, Natural landscape, scenic beauty

2. INTRODUCTION

Eco-tourism is derived from two words- Ecosystem & Tourism. Ecotourism ,a newly developed concept is a bridge between the nature and modern life style. It is the most fascinating form of the nature based tourism. Ecosystem is the system in which we live include the earth, the water, the sky, and living and non living objects which embraces the principles of sustainable tourism (www.ecotourism.org). Eco -tourism is not only travelling to such ecosystems, but also conserving them. Ideal ecotourism should be beneficial for everyone involved-tour operators, government, visitors and local residents. The strategy for the development of tourism in the Wayanad has to be consistent with the geographical

features of the area. Government, private enterprises, local communities and NGO'S all have an important role to play. Ecosystem or natural environment is the base for the development of eco-tourism.

Wayanad, one of the most popular tourist destinations of Kerala is showing a steady growth in the business. The Western Ghats, Waterfalls, paddy fields and verdant green hills create a postcard-perfect landscape in Wayanad. Apart from this, the soothing climate attracts large numbers of domestic and foreign tourists to enjoy the scenic beauty of Wayanad (www.Kerala.org).

3. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1. The main objective of this study is to understand the role scenic beauty of a place has in the growth of Ecotourism.
2. To recognise the key environmental, social, and economic impacts of growth of Ecotourism

4. DEFINITIONS OF ECOTOURISM

The term "Ecotourism" was first heard in the 1980's, the first broadly accepted definition and one which continues to be alive, was established by the International Ecotourism Society in 1990 and is as given below.

"Responsible travel to natural areas that conserves the environment and improves the well being of local people"

A new definition has been adopted by World Conservation Union (IUCN, 1997) in 1996 which describes ecotourism as: "Ecotourism is responsible travel and visitation to natural areas in order to enjoy and appreciate nature that promotes conservation, have a low visitor impact and provide for beneficially active socio-economic involvement of local people"

Eco-tourism is derived from two words- 'Ecosystem & Tourism '. To understand Eco-tourism we have to understand our Ecosystem first. Ecosystem is the system is the system in which we live, the system which include the earth, the water, the sky and of course the living and the non-living objects in all these system. Eco-tourism is not only travelling to such Ecosystems, but also conserving them.

The following elements are crucial to the ultimate success of an ecotourism –

- Have a low impact upon a potential area’s natural resources:
- Involve stakeholders (individuals, communities, ecotourism, tour operators and government institutions) in the planning, development, implementation and monitoring phases.

FIGURE 1: ECOTOURISM AND ASSOCIATED BENEFITS

TABLE 1: RANK ORDER OF ECOTOURISM POTENTIAL OF DISTRICTS IN KERALA

DISTRICT	SCORE	RANK
IDUKKI	198	1
WAYANAD	189	2
KOTTAYAM	176	3
THRISSUR	169	4
PATHANAMTHITTA	166	5
PALAKKAD	158	6
TRIVANDRUM	157	7
KOZHICODE	151	8
KOLLAM	150	9
KANNUR	141	10
MALAPPURAM	133	11
KASARGOD	123	12
ERNAKULAM	74	13
ALAPPUZHA	48	14

SCORE

6. ECO_TOURISM IN KERALA

India's most loved tropical paradise Kerala boasts of some of the richest biodiversity in the world. Popularly known as the Gods own country, Kerala is today one of the most sought after tourist destinations in Asia. Located at the southernmost tip of India, Kerala is a 560 km long, narrow stretch of land. The land blessed by the God, is higher in diversity with the climate more humid and wetter. Kerala represents one of India's 3 richest tropical moist forest areas. This part of the country with wet evergreen forest has the most complex and species rich vegetation in the country. Kerala is also endowed with a number of other tourist attractions and options including beach tourism, forests, wildlife and landscapes for ecotourism. (Journal eco tourism 2005)

. The key elements of Ecotourism include a natural environment friendly visitor, activities that do not have any serious impact on the ecosystem and the positive involvement of local community in maintaining ecological balance. The research paper also focuses mainly on the ecotourism resources in Kerala especially in Wayanad and formulate strategies for the development of Waianae's eco-tourism potentials through the concentrated efforts of all key players such as Government, local authorities, the developers and the operators, the visitors and local community.(journal eco tourism2006) .Tourism in the ecologically sensitive areas needed eco-tourism development. An example of ecotourism practices in Wayanad is

discussed below. (Ecotourism in Kerala, Department of Publications, Government of Kerala, 1999.)

7. LOCATION OF WAYANAD IN KERALA

District of Wayanad is on the southern tip of the Deccan plateau. On its North, South and West lay the districts of Kannur, Malappuram and Kozhikode (Calicut) respectively. To its North and East, it borders the Karnataka districts of Coorg and Mysore. Further to the southeast lies the Nilgiri district of Tamilnadu. Kalpetta is the District Headquarters. Sultan Bathery and Mananthavady are the other towns.

8. HIGHLIGHT TOURIST ATTRACTIONS IN WAYANAD

8.1. POOKOT LAKE

This perennial fresh water lake, nestled among wooded hills, is the only one of its kind in Kerala. A fresh water aquarium with large variety of fish is an added attraction. Tourists can also avail of boating facilities, Children Park, and a shopping centre for handicrafts and spices.

8.2 EDAKKAL CAVES:

The 2 caves are located at a height of 1000 meter on Ambukutty Hill near Ambalavayal. The new Stone Age pictorial writings on the walls of these natural caves at Edakkal are evidence of the civilization that existed in Wayanad in prehistoric times.

8.3 LAKKADI:

Lakkadi is the gateway to Wayanad. It is situated 700 meter above mean sea level, at the crest of the Thamarassery Ghat pass. Luxuriant forests, lofty peaks, gurgling streams and a good number of monkeys on both sides give thrill to the journey up the winding hill station.

8.4 PAKSHIPATHALAM:

Rare species of birds can be sighted from the watch tower of this bird's sanctuary. This place can be accessed only by trekking.

8.5 KURUVA DWEEP: (Island)

[Anita Jose & Siby. C. Chithran / Protection of Nature's Scenic Beauty has An Important Role in The Growth of Ecotourism](#)

The Kuruva Island is a 950 acre of ever green forest lying on the tributaries of east flowing river Kabani. It is an ideal picnic spot, far away from the disturbance of city life. The island is inhabited. Rare species of birds, orchids and herbs are found here.

8.6 PAZHASSI TOMB:

King Pazhassi, known as the “lion of Kerala”, who organized guerrilla type warfare against British East India company, was cremated in Mananthavady in 1805.

8.7 THIRUNELLI TEMPLE:

Thirunelli is situated north -east of Mananthavady under the Brahmagiri hills in the reserve forests. The temple is a marvel of architecture. The shrine is shielded with 30 granite columns and the ground is paved with huge square pieces of granite. The crystal clear waters of the Papanasini River running downhill add to the enchantment of the place. Pakshipathalam, an interesting trekking centre, is 7 kms away from the temple.

8.8 MUTHANGA WILD LIFE SANCTUARY:

Thick forests covering an area of 345 sq.kms forms the Muthanga Wild Life sanctuary – the biggest abode of wild animals in north Kerala. Elephant, spotted deer, bison, tiger, cheetah, wild bear, etc are found in this sanctuary. The forest department has facilities for providing elephant rides to tourists. Muthanga, which is 16 kms east of Sulthan Bathery, is located very near to the Karnataka boarder.

8.9 NAGARHOLE WILD LIFE SANCTARY:

It extends over an area of 635 sq. Kms. The park houses diverse species of plant and animal life. Elephants roam freely. Tigers are seen frequently. Various species of deer, monkeys, birds etc are also found here.

8.10 CHEMBRA PEAK:

At 2100 meter above mean sea level, Chembra is the highest peak in Wayanad and is an ideal area for trekking. Climbing this peak is a challenging Endeavour and would take a full day.

8.11 SOOCHIPPARA WATERFALL:

The waterfall at Soochippara near Meppadi is really a treasure of nature. The waterfall ranging at places from 100 to 300 feet height is a treat to the eyes. The pool below provides for water rafting, swimming, bathing etc.

8.12 BANASURA SAGAR DAM:

This is the largest earth dam in India. The topography here is such that many islands will be formed in the upstream of the dam when the dam is full. These islands with the back ground of the Banasura hill will provide an enchanting sight to tourists. Boating facilities are available here.

9.1 HEAVENLY HEIGHTS OF WAYANAD

In the central area of the district, hills are lower in height, while in northern parts the hills are with mountainous appearance. Some of the major peaks in Wayanad are Chembra, Vellarimala, Banasura, Brahmagiri etc.

Chembra is situated in Mepadi Panchayat of Vythiri Taluk. It is the highest peak in Wayanad at a height of 1843 meters above the sea level. Chembra is a part of Western Ghats. Chembra one of the favourite tourist spots for trekking and sightseeing. A walk through the Chembra trail amidst the plantation, offers a soothing experience to the travellers.

Phantom Rock is a natural union of rocks. It is said that the rock is formed because of an Earthquake. Another attraction Sunrise Valley is located at 27 kms from the district headquarters, Kalpetta. An interesting trek up the Ambukuthi hill near Ambalavayal town takes us to the fascinating Neolithic cave site of Edakkal. Etchings found on the walls of these caves have drawn the serious attention of archaeologists and historians worldwide. With at least three distinct sets of petroglyph, it is thought to date back over 5000 years.

Vellarimala is one of the most beautiful hill stations in Kerala. Vellari with its unique geographical position, gorgeous waterfalls, thick forests shrouded in mist and unique flora, is becoming a popular trekking destination. Vellarimala forms part of a high hill range of what is otherwise known as Camel's Hump Mountains, a part of the Western Ghats.

Lakkadi view point is one of the highest locations in Wayanad. It is at an elevation of 700 meters above sea level. It's a great place to watch sun rise and sun set and on a clear sunny day, the view is mesmerizing. The view from the top also offers a bird's view of lofty

mountain peaks, the gurgling stream, luxuriant vegetation & winding roads that are really awesome.

9.2 WATERFALLS OF WAYANAD -GOODNESS OF NATURE'S

The waterfalls of Wayanad provide yet another awesome sight which attracts nature lovers from across the globe. Meenmutty, soochippara, are some of the major waterfalls of Wayanad. Soochippara waterfalls are really a treasure of nature. Soochippara is a 3-tiered powerful waterfall with a height of 300 meters. The cliff face here is ideal for rock climbing. Meenmutty waterfall is the largest and most spectacular waterfall in Wayanad. It is Kerala's second largest waterfall and one of the most unspoiled in its natural setting.

Kanthanpara waterfall is located at a distance of about 8 km from Meppadi town and is an easily accessible get away. The natural scenic beauty offered by the tea estates on both sides of the road from Meppadi adds to the excitement. Kanthanpara is an admirable cascading water body which is about 30 meters in height. This place is ideal for trekking and birding. The place is mysteriously silent and the path that leads to the waterfall is surrounded by bamboo trees.

Chethalayam is a small but attractive waterfall located at a distance of 12 kms from Sulthan Bathery, the nearest town. It's a lovely place to visit during monsoon and adventure enthusiasts will have a real good time climbing up the rock surfaces. The surroundings offer a number of points for bird -watching.

10. TRIBAL CUISINES AND MEDICINES OF WAYANAD

The Wayanad Forests are one of the main sources for medicinal and life giving herbs, fruits and vegetables, one who knows the secrets of these are the tribes. Forest of Wayanad is the home to a number of indigenous tribes. Where the ingredients of various ethnic food items unique to their lifestyle are procured and these tribes still believe and practice their traditional medicines which involve a variety of wild herbs. There are many tribes in this area and actually the story of Wayanad is the story of tribals.

Vellan vaidyar of Thirunelli and Keluvaidyar of Kattikulam belong to the Kurichya tribe and both are famous for their traditional way of treatment based on wild herbs. Vellanvaidyar are famous for the treatment of cancer, paralysis, fractured bones, asthma, diabetes etc. As per

tribal customs, the ingredients used in the preparation of medicines are always kept as a secret.

10.1 VELLAN -TRIBAL COOK OF WAYAND

Vellan prepares varieties of tribe dishes like boiled wild tubers with honey, bamboo rice payasam, grilled chicken, fried rock crabs, fried mushroom, muddha vada, karakkundappam, kallu puttu, coconut rice, pollayappam and so on. Vellan's signature masala has made of green pepper, cloves, forest cinnamon, nutmeg, garlic, sarvasugandhi and so on. The rock crabs are usually collected from the cracks of rocks in the nearby rivers. 'Gandhakasala' rice, a scented rice variety of Wayanad, is the main ingredient of the items such as coconut rice, kalluputtu, pollayappam and Karakkundappam.

11. PARADISE FOR BIRD LOVERS

Cradled amidst the pristine forests of Western Ghats, Wayanad holds a myriad of bewitching beauties of nature. Almost all of the Western Ghats endemics can be spotted in the forests of Wayanad. Wayanad has got bamboo forests, plantations, evergreen forests etc. Each of these locations promises enough winged wonders which will satiate the eyes of the birding enthusiast. Wayanad is also having a good area of paddy fields which attract a good number of waders and other such birds during winter. Snipes, sandpipers, egrets, ducks and cormorants enjoy the bounty offered by the fertile land.

12. WONDERFUL : A SYNONYM FOR WAYAND

Wayanad is by the Mother Nature; its vast stretches of mist capped mountains, green meadows of valleys, while water springs, blue water lakes and wild forests fabricate the splendid natural beauty. Wayanad is situated on the crest of Western Ghats. The unique geographical setting along with its salubrious climate and rich history makes Wayanad an entity, which is a unique tourism product. The Wayanad hills acts as a hub of attractions. This destination is ideal for sightseeing as well as trekking, mountaineering rock climbing etc. The waterfalls of Wayanad provide yet another awesome sight which attracts nature lovers from across the globe. Wayanad has greenery everywhere, pleasing picnic spots, attractive waterfalls, reservoirs, spectacular wild life with luxuriant forests and the best accommodation with home like hospitality.

13. VILLAGE LIFE EXPERIENCE IN WAYANAD

Village life experience packages offer the chance to experience the real charm of village life. VLE packages offer the guests to experience varieties from the typical sceneries. Tourists are coming for a vacation for an enjoyment and the interaction with the local people they are getting more knowledge about the community and the new village life experiences. This also will help tourist to understand traditional labour, life style and farming practices.

In Wayanad district two VLE packages are operating. These 2 packages focus on the Ethnic life styles. One is located at Nellarachal, the beautiful village near Karappuzha Dam. In the Nellarachal package a guest can experience the charisma of a traditional village. Here a tourist can endure how vellan can make the traditional tribal art instrument “Thudy “ and enjoy its sweet music. Chettyalathoor, the next package area is located 17 km from Sulltan Bathery. In this package you get the chance to visit Bamboo craft centre by Murukeshan and he will take you through the age old process used to create the famous bamboo products. And also get a chance to have a look at the ancient tools and weapons used by the tribes for cultivation on display.

Village life experience package offers you to experience the simple life of a village. This is an Endeavour that distributes the benefits of tourism to the local community, thus making it meaningful and mutually beneficial.

14. IMPACT OF GROWTH OF ECOTOURISM THROUGH THE GROWTH OF NATURAL BEAUTY IN WAYANAD

1. Lack of government initiatives to improve the infrastructure facilities, connectivity between different tourist destinations in Wayanad.
2. As a tourism destination, needs more media attention and support for development.
3. Need more attention to protect our environment and climate to sustain the natural beauty of the destination.
4. Need a joint effort from the Governments, stakeholders, other departments and the local people for the promotion of the destination.

15. A CONCEPTUAL MODEL WHICH EXPLAINS THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN NATURAL SCENIC BEAUTY AND ECOTOURISM GROWTH IN WAYANAD

Figure 1: NATURAL BEAUTY AND ECOTOURISM GROWTH IN WAYANAD

Figure 2(Conceptual model for the development of Ecotourism)

Research Methodology

<p><u>Stages of research</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Selection of case study sites and collection of secondary sources • Interview with key industry representatives. • Interview with ecotourism stakeholders. • Interview with tourists 	<p><u>Objectives</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To find the role of stake holders in promoting ecotourism in destinations. • To understand issues and problems for case study sites. • To develop definitions and actions of ecotourism • To identify the major problems and prospects of ecotourism initiatives in Kerala
--	--

17. FINDINGS

Wayanad can be viewed as a typical ecotourism destination in all aspects. It conserves nature, participates and benefits local community and maintains sustainability. Wayanad is the only destination which has access from all nearby states of Kerala. A joint effort by the Government, stakeholders, other departments and the local people is a must if we need to make this a reality. At present Climate change , Unlimited building construction, Tourist overflow, Lack of trained naturalist and guides ,Lack of awareness of tourists to protect nature, Lack of knowledge of stakeholders for protecting the beauty of the nature are the problems affecting the growth of ecotourism in Wayanad. Government must take initiatives to improve the infrastructure facilities, connectivity between different tourist destinations in Wayanad. Wayanad is a very sensitive destination, which needs to be handled with lot of care. The Government must have a proper control on tourism development to make the destination more tourist friendly

18. CONCLUSIONS

POSITIVE & NEGATIVE IMPACTS OF GROWTH OF ECOTOURISM IN WAYANAD

POSITIVE IMPACTS	NEGATIVE IMPACTS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Conservation of natural areas *Contributions to Government revenues *Improved environmental management and planning *Improvement of Environmental quality *Protection and Preservation of Nature *Alternative Employment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> *When the level of visitor use is greater than the environment’s ability to cope with this use within the acceptable limit of change. *Uncontrolled conventional tourism poses potential threats to many natural areas around the world. *Depletion of natural resources such as; Natural resources, local resources, land resources

REFERENCES

- [1]. Ecotourism in Kerala, Department of Publications, Government of Kerala, 1999.
- [2]. Mridula, Narayan Dutt, “Ecology and Tourism “, Universal Publishers, New Delhi 1997.
- [3]. Dixon, J A, LF Scura, RA Karpenter and Pitfalls “, Washington, D.C, WWF.
- [4]. www.ecotourism.org.
- [5]. Goodwin, H. (2008a) “Tourism, local economic development and poverty reduction”, Applied Research in Economic Development, 5 (3), 55-64
- [6]. Sustainable Tourism Bruce Poon Tip, International Trade forum, 2009
- [7]. Winston Husbands & Lynn C. Harrison, Practicing Responsible Tourism, 1996 pp. xiii + 590 pp. ISBN 0-471-12236-X
- [8]. Kerala’s Approach to Tourism Development: A Case Study Ministry of Tourism & Culture, Government of India
- [9]. Evaluation Study in Selected Overseas Markets Ministry of Tourism, Govt. of India
- [10]. Sustainable and Responsible Tourism; Trends, Practices and cases, edited by Parikshat Singh Manhas 2012.

[Anita Jose & Siby. C. Chithran / Protection of Nature's Scenic Beauty has An Important Role in The Growth of Ecotourism](#)

- [11] Ecotourism Resources in India; an Integrated Development Approach; A case study by Kerala Institute of Tourism and Travel study
- [13] Journal eco tourism 2005,
- [14] Journal eco tourism 2006
- [15] Journal eco tourism 2007
- [16] Journal eco tourism vol. 4, No1
- [17] Journal eco tourism vol. 3, No3
- [18] R.K Maikhuri, U.Rana, K.S. Rao, K.G Saxena (2000). International Journal of Sustainable and world Ecology.
- [19] UNEP (2011); Making Tourism More Sustainable, A guide for Policy Makers.
- [20] Williams, A.M & Shaw, G (1988). Tourism and development, In Tourism Economic Development: Western European Experiences, A.M. Williams and G. Smith (Eds). London, England; Belhaven Press
- [21] www.Keralatourism.gov.in.
- [22] New Zealand (2007) New Zealand Tourism strategy 2015, Wellington: Ministry of Tourism.